

Role of PMKVY in Promoting Employability Skills and Placement in Haryana State

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The purpose of this study is to define the role of PMKVY in promoting employability skills and placement in Haryana state. The study is based on secondary sources of data. Data are collected about the 10 training partners having 68 training centers. Through this study highlighted the training centers are qualifying for performance-based target reallocation or not. The India skills report 2019 states that around 70% of the youth are facing problems due to a lack of professional guidance in finding desirable jobs that worth their skills. PMKVY was launched on July 16, 2015, for the individuals who are unemployed, school dropouts and want to train under a particular sector. The main focus is to be given on the structure of training centers in Haryana and their placement performance.

Keywords: Training Partner, Placement Performance, Training Centers

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Introduction

Employability skills are defined as the skill earned by the employee to be winning attention upon the workforce with whom the set organizational goals are realized. At the present time, most of the persons face the problems of unemployment and their skills not fitted as per the requirements of the organizations. Due to the lack of formal vocational education for a huge sector of this population leads to poor effectiveness, output, and low-income levels.

PMKVY (Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana) is a scheme was launched on July 16, 2015, to give a new direction of Indian youth who are facing the problems of unemployment. The objective PMKVY to provide short term training programme and enhance the standards of living of Indian youth and secured a better livelihood. "Skilled is building a better India. If we have to move India towards development, then skill development should be our mission." Shri Narendra Modi (Prime Minister of India) Red Fort, Delhi August 2014. As of 15th January 2017, 1100, training centers have been on boarded under PMKVY. "We are a young nation. Our youth is our strength. The world and India need a skilled workforce." Shri Rajiv Pratap Rudy, Minister of State (Independent charge) for skill development and entrepreneurship. Skill development must have linkages with social and economic development goals and programs were like "Make in India," "Digital India," "Swachh Bharat," and Smart Cities." As per the report of the sub-group of Chief Minister on Skill Development (September 2015) NSDC (National Skill Development Council) provides concessional loans (soft loans) to training partners covering up to 85% of the total project investment to cover the expenditure related to a training program.

The benefits of PMKVY highlighted that is fostered for inclusive growth and works in union with various other Government projects and scheme and treated schemes like Make in India, Digital India, Pradhan Mantri Mudra loans and Pradhan Mantri Bima Yojana. A total of 54% has been placed under PMKVY in India comparatively 52% female, 48% male and 0.001% transgender. Overall the participation of female candidates is higher than male candidates. If we are going back and looking at the history then find

Out that the participation of the training partners, training job roles, training centers, and total certified trainees who have completed the training under PMKVY increase continuous and the ratio of total placed candidates decrease.

Review of Related Literature

Palit (2009) found that higher education capacities in India are irregularly spread across the country. India's formal technical training infrastructure was much more controlled than the necessities. Particular technical training was offered for different disciplines within the broader ambit of agriculture, engineering, and technology, 90% of the diploma programmes and 80% of the certificate training programmes are in engineering subjects. The researchers used factors, such as the share of different disciplines in India's higher education institutions. **Khan, Khan, and Khan (2011)** focused upon training and development, on the job training, training design and delivery style on organizational performance. Highlighted that best skills may be arises through training and their smooth development. The main objective of the study was to identify how training increases employee performance. The data were collected from 100 respondents. The analysis was made with the help of descriptive statistics and the Z-test. Data was based on primary as well as secondary sources. The study found that on the job training is very effective and also saves time and cost.

Okada (2012) identified that India is in front of very complicated and wonderful challenges in bringing up the skills among youths, for various reasons. The researchers identify challenges facing skills development efforts, large youth population, estimated population of India by age group, the structure of labor market in India, distribution of rural and urban workers in India, value-added as a percentage of GDP, distribution of formal and informal manufacturing firms in India, trends in the educational composition of the Indian workforce by gender and by location, income and types of occupation of employed males and females aged 15 to 59, by the level of education, education and training opportunities for Indian youth, skills development opportunities outside the formal education system, trends in an apprenticeship in India, enterprise-based training, recent development in skills development

For the youth. **Bhiwa (2012)** defines the current circumstances of the education system in India and highlighted the role of skill development in trade and industry growth. The study establishes various factors such as the UN human development index of G 20 countries, part of skill development for economic growth, government initiative for skill development, national skill Development Corporation, national knowledge commission and security exchange board of India.

Punjani (2014) highlighted that the economy could be converted into more dynamic innovative and competitive through the subsistence of more skilled human potential. The objective of the study was to analyze the requirement and p level of skill development in India. The data were collected from secondary sources and used a descriptive research design. The study found that the existing skill development policy in India requires vital treatment. The main findings of the study reveal that only 10% of the Indian workforce has formal training. **Yadav (2014)** defined that the various issues like unintentional rural-urban journey population growth, high school dropout rates. The researchers studied the factors seating capacity, vocational education, management & governance, faculty development, and industry participation. The study found that introducing personal management of institutions in dynamic manner levels to enhance employability skills.

Saini (2015) traced out that both the Government and its partner agencies have undertaken various procedures for the effective execution of the skill development system in the economy, but still are facing several uncertain issues/challenges that need an immediate concentration of the policymakers. The study found that as more as India moves towards the knowledge economy; it becomes progressively more essential for it to focus on the innovation of the skills. **Misra (2015)** examined to generate a skilled labor force through the successful use of a scheme of Government of India to instruct 500 million people by 2022. The main objectives of the study were to recognize the present skill development policy initiatives in India and find out the behavior and earnings to produce world-class skilled manpower domestically through effective use of skill development schemes

Of the Government of India. The researchers used various factors such as pathways to address the problem, policy alternative to status point of view, national skill Development Corporation, and existing skill delivery framework of India, restructuring of skill development mission and proposed structure of skill development mission. Found that there are lots of challenges in the way of achieving targets such as quality of training, standardization of curriculum, recognition of course globally, etc.

Kalita and Sharma (2016) stated the level of skill education in the brass metal industry of Assam and how it contributes towards the reinforcement of the in poor health industries in this sector examined the world market has distorted quickly for the skilled and unskilled workforce, and there is increasing necessitate for workers with specific skills. The researchers analyze the problems faced by the artisans and Government initiatives taken in the field of skill development in the brass metal industry. The study found out no Government initiative has been taken up to analyze training in this ground in recent years. **Aggarwal (2016)** defined the present skill capacity and the challenges faced by the skill development system in India along with their solutions. The researcher used various factors such as demand & supply mismatch, geographical problem, low educational attainment, vocational training, and skill development for women. The study found that both the government and its partner agencies have launched various measures for the effective performance of the skill development system in the economy. **Kumar (2017)** examined the current state of education and skill development system. The researcher stated that Bihar is one of the best-growing economies (approx 10.6 %) during the last decade showing a remarkable phenomenon. Skills development tries to improve access to skills development at IT's for women, disadvantaged groups (SC, ST, and OBCs), minorities, disabled and economically challenged people. The study found that the Bihar moves towards the understanding economy; it becomes progressively more essential for it to focus on the expansion of the skills which are relevant to the rising economic environment.

Devi (2017) examined the concept of skill development in India, the programs and policies

That have been initiated for skill development. The main objective of the study was to recommend a structural and sensible solution to address the lack of significant skills amongst the current and prospective workforce of India and to recognize the challenges in skill development. The researcher studied the various factors i.e., national skill development and entrepreneurship policy the national skill development mission, skill India campaign, the study stated the concept of skill development has been largely recognized and many programs and policies are being formulated to initiate skill development concept not only in urban areas but in rural areas also. **Pandey and Nema (2017)** explored the hurdles faced by the youth to realize the skill India development programme on all fronts. The purposive sampling technique was used to select the sample for the study. The sample size was 60 respondents. The study found that 56% of the respondents were opposite the problems of unemployment. The majority of selected respondents were educated up to secondary level.

Shrivastav and Jatav (2017) analyzed the Indian experience of skill development, and the challenges faced for skill development in provisions of financial resources examined that the difficulty to fill up the jobs is 48%, which is above the global standard of 34% in 2012. The researchers suggested that there should be an assured amount of remuneration to be paid for vocational students, which will give confidence to the students to choose for professional training. **Kumar (2018)** examined the skill India campaign along with make in India, Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana, and Deen Dayal Upadhyaya Gramin Kaushal Yojana for the skill development of growing youth. The main objective of the study was to know the present scenario of skill in India. The study used various factors such as the need for skill development in India, present scenario of skill in India, recent scheme for skill development in India such as PMKVY, DDU-GKY (Deen Dayal Upadhyaya Gramin Kaushal Yojana), STEP (Support to Training and Employment Programme for Women), PMMY (Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana). **Raj (2018)** attempt has been made to recognize which kind of hurdles Indian workforce/students face to accomplish skill development at all fronts. The study observed various

Factors such as the scope of vocational or technical education in India, challenges, government initiatives and use of technology in rural education of India. The study found that the PMKVY envisaged as a key measure to impart skill-based training to young men and women, making them talented in earning and sustaining the nation's anti-poverty activities.

Research Gap

On the basis of the review of literature, it has been observed that a few researchers have attempted to study skill development and employability skills. No, any study has been conducted to identify the role of training partners and their training centers in promoting employability skills and their placement performance. To bridge the gap, this study has been conducted to identify the combination of skill employability promoting by training partners and their training centers through the PMKVY scheme.

Research Methodology

The objective of the study

Sample size - 10 training partners and their 68 training centers

01. To describe the structure of training partners under PMKVY
02. To assess the performance of the placement of training partners under PMKVY
03. To show the target reallocation status and category of training partners

Data Analysis and Interpretations

The table-1 is showing 32 sector skill councils and the no. of job roles offered by them. The table depicts that the handicraft and carpet sector skill council offering the highest job roles and stand the first place. Whereas lower job role available in the tourism and hospitality sector skill council, life sciences sector skill council, and Indian plumbing skill council.

Table-1 Sector Skill Councils and Job Roles (Annexure 1)

Analysis of Figure-1 Sector Skill Council and Job Roles

The table-2 is showing the district-wise training centers in Haryana after a complete analysis finds out that Hisar has a maximum training center is 26 in Haryana and Charkhi Dadri has the lowest training centers. Jhajjar, Kaithal, Kurukshetra, and Sonipat have an equal training center that is 10.

Table-2 District-Wise Training Centers in Haryana

District	No. of Training Center	District	No. of Training Center	District	Training Center
Ambala	16	Kaithal	10	Rewari	07
Bhiwani	22	Karnal	13	Rohtak	09
Charkhi Dadri	06	Kurukshetra	10	Sirsa	24
Faridabad	23	Mahendragarh	17	Sonipat	10
Fatehabad	15	Mewat	16	Yamunanagar	13
Gurugram	21	Palwal	11	Jind	20
Hisar	26	Panchkula	16		
Jhajjar	10	Panipat	11		

Sources: -<https://pmkvyofficial.org/find-a-training-centre>.

Analysis of Figure-2 District-Wise Training Centers in Haryana

Find out that the majority of the training centers are highest in Hisar and Sirsa district i.e. is 26 and 24 then the next steps comes to the Faridabad district then comes to the Bhiwani, Gurugram and Ambala. Mewat has also highest training centers as compare to Charkhi Dadri and Rewari.

Table-3 Structure of Skill Development Training Centers in Haryana (Annexure 2)

Role of Training Partner in Promoting Employability Skills in Haryana (2016-2018)

01. **Centum work skills India Limited-** find out that the placement performance of CWSI PMKK, Hisar is highest but the 1st-month record closure for validation is not provided and the training centers qualifying for performance-based target reallocation. PMKK-Sirsa placement performance is denoted 0.0% but the training centers qualifying for performance-based target reallocation.

Figure-3 Placement Performance of Centum Work Skills India Ltd.

2. **Aitmc ventures Private Limited-** when the analysis is to be made then find out that the Aitmc ventures provide a wonder placement in all centers available in Haryana. It has 11 training centers in Haryana. All training centers provide more than 82.2% placements. It has the highest score in all Haryana. Training centers qualified for the target-based reallocation process and also submitted a 1st-month record for validation.

Figure-4 Placement Performance of Aitmc Ventures Private Ltd.

3. Orion Edutech Private Limited- when the analysis is to be made that then finds out that Orion Edutech has five training centers in Haryana. The majority of the training centers to provide placement highest in PMKK-Rohtak is highest is 59.9% and the lowest placement is 32.7% the training centers available in Bhiwani. Training centers are not providing 1st-month record closure for validation and the training centers not qualified for performance-based target allocation.

Figure-5 Placement Performance of Orion Edutech Private Ltd.

4. R.M. Education and Welfare Society- when the analysis is to be made that then finds out that B.R.M. has 17 training centers in Haryana. The majority of the training centers to provide placement highest in new star skill development institute Faridabad is 91.5% and the lowest placement is 71.8 % the training centers available in Fatehabad. Out of 17, five training centers are not providing 1st-month record closure for validation and the training centers not qualified for performance-based target allocation.

Figure-6 Placement Performance of B.R.M. Education and Welfare Society

5. Advance Smart Skills Private Limited- when the analysis is to be made that then find out that advance smart skills private limited has four training centers in Haryana. The majority of the training centers to provide placement highest in BMD training center in Mahendragarh is 79.0% and the lowest placement is 75.6 % the training centers available in also Mahendragarh. All four training centers are not providing 1st-month record closure for validation and the training centers not qualified for performance-based target allocation.

Figure-7 Placement Performance of Advance Smart Skills Private Ltd.

6. BDM Institute Skill Development- when the analysis is to be made that then finds out that BDM Institute skill development has six training centers in Haryana. The majority of the training centers to provide placement highest in four training centers is 100%. But three training centers are not providing 1st-month record closure for validation and all the six training centers not qualified for performance-based target reallocation.

Figure-8 Placement performance of BDM Institute Skill Development

7. Brilliant Education Society- brilliant education society has only one training center in Yamunanagar. It is providing 40.6%

Placement and the training centers are not providing 1st-month record closure for validation and not qualified for performance-based target reallocation.

Figure-9 Placement Performance of Brilliant Education Society

8. Brilliant Education Society- brilliant education society has only one training center in Yamunanagar. It is providing 40.6% placement and the training centers are not providing 1st-month record closure for validation and not qualified for performance-based target reallocation.

Figure-9 Placement Performance of Brilliant Education Society

9. R. Dadhich Memorial Society- C.R. Dadhich has 11 training centers in Haryana. Out of the 11 training centers, the highest placement providing by the oxford skill development institution is 97.6% and the lowest placement provided by the Panchal skill training center is 0.0%. Four training centers are not providing 1st-month record closure for validation and all 11 not qualified for performance-based target reallocation.

Figure-10 Placement Performance of C.R. Dadhich Memorial Society

9. Directorate of Indian Army Veterans- directorate of Indian army veterans has two training centers in Haryana one is in Ambala Cantt and the second is Chandimandir. But the placement details of both centers are 0.0%. Training centers do not provide 1st-month record closure for validation and not qualified for performance-based target reallocation.

Figure-11 Placement performance of Directorate of Indian Army Veterans

10. DP Education Society- DP education society has 03 training centers in Haryana. All of the training centers provide the highest placement lies 71% to 86% but training centers are not provide 1st-month record closure for validation and not qualified for performance-based target reallocation.

Figure-12 Placement Performance of DP Education Society

Placement Performance of Training Partners- highlighted the name of the training partner, training centers, placement performance, and 1st-month record closure for validation, and training centers qualifying for performance-based target reallocation.

Table-4 Placement Performance of Training Partners (Annexure 3)

Categories of Target Re-allocation- basically six types of categories provided by the NSDC (National Skill Development Council) give the target based on job roles. First categories A, provided those training centers who provided more than 70% placement and also submitted employment record, categories B, provided more than 70% placement but not submitted employment record, categories C, old franchises training centers reported 70 % placement along with employment record, categories D, old franchises training centers reported 70% or more placement but not provided training centers level verification, Categories E, training centers do not qualify for target reallocation, and categories E provide PMKKs and Govt. MoU training centers. Table -5 define the different- different categories this can be explained as follow :-

Table-5 Categories of Target Re-allocation (Annexure 4)

Finding and Conclusions

When we divided the training centers as per the categories of reallocation then found that out of 68 training centers only 17 training centers covered in the categories A, training centers which have reported more than 70% placement with 1st-month employment record/received and have completed training center level verification. 15 training centers covered in the categories B, training centers which have reported more than 70% placement with 1st-month employment record/ training center level verification is not received. No anyone training centers covered in the categories C, old franchises training centers which have reported more than 70% placement with 1st-month employment record received and have completed training center level verification. Only four training centers covered in the categories D, old franchises training centers which have reported more than 70% placement with 1st-month employment record/training center level verification is not received. 20 training centers covered in the categories E, training centers not qualifying for performance-based target reallocation and 12 training centers covered in the categories F, PMKKs and Government MOU training centers The majority of the training centers covered in the categories E, training centers not qualifying for performance-based target reallocation is highest.

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(Annexure 1)

Table-1 Sector Skill Councils and Job Roles

Sr. No.	Sector Skill Councils	No. of Courses/Job Roles
1.	Agricultural Sector Skill Council of India	39
2.	Apparel, Made-Ups, Home Furnishing Sector Skill Councils	14
3.	Automotive skill development council	51
4.	Beauty & wellness sector skill council	07
5.	BFSI sector skill council of India	08
6.	Capital goods skill council	21
7.	Construction skill development council of India	22
8.	Domestic workers sector skill council	15
9.	Electronics sector skill council	11
10.	Food industry capacity and skill initiative (FICSI)	06
11.	Furniture and fittings skill council	05
12.	Gem and jewellery skill council of India	24
13.	Handicraft and carpet sector skill council	100
14.	Healthcare sector skill council	21
15.	Indian iron and steel sector skill council	36
16.	Indian plumbing skill council	07
17.	Infrastructure equipment skill council	17
18.	IT/ITeS sector skill council	06
19.	Leather sector skill council	21
20.	Life sciences sector skill development council	01
21.	Logistics sector skill council	18
22.	Media and entertainment skill council	22
23.	Mining sector skill council of India	15
24.	Power sector skill council	05
25.	Retailers associations skill council of India	05
26.	Rubber skill development council	20
27.	Skill council for green jobs	05
28.	Skill council for persons with disability	06
29.	Security service skill council	02
30.	Telecom sector skill council	12
31.	Textile sector skill council (TSC)	47
32.	Tourism and hospitality sector skill council	04

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- <https://www.slideshare.net/ZahidHusain4/pmkvy-survey-and-development-process> accessed on 22 April, 2019 at 1:48 p.m.

(Annexure 2)

Table-3 Structure of Skill Development Training Centers in Haryana

Sr. No.	Name of the training partner	Place	Nature of skill
1.	Abhigyan Skill Training Private Limited	Bhiwani	Persons with disability
2.	Aitmc Ventures Pvt. Ltd.	Hisar, Sirsa	Electronic and hardware, Apparel, IT-ITeS, Power, Logistics
3.	Advance smart skills private limited	Charkhi Dadri, Mahendragarh,	Electronic and hardware, Logistics, Power, Agriculture, Apparel
4.	BDM institute skill development	Bhiwani,	Power
5.	B.R.M. education and welfare society	Fatehabad, Hisar, Sirsa	Apparel, Electronic and hardware, Logistics
6.	Brilliant Education society	Yamunanagar	Logistics
7.	C.R. Dadhich Memorial Society	Fatehabad	Apparel, Electronic and hardware

8.	Centum work skills India Limited	Fatehabad, Hisar, Jind, Kaithal, Sirsa	Telecom, Tourism & Hospitality, Apparel, Beauty and wellness, Iron and steel, Logistics, Healthcare, Domestic worker, Electronic and hardware
9.	Directorate of Indian Army Veterans (DIAV)	Ambala, Hisar, Panchkula	Apparel, Beauty and wellness
10.	DP Education Society	Faridabad, Palwal	Electronic and hardware, Persons with disability, Retail, Media and entertainment
11.	Dr. B R Ambedkar Nav Vidya Jyoti Education Trust	Karnal, Kurukshetra	Power
12.	Dr. Ambedkar Education Trust Maya Puri	Yamunanagar	Logistics
13.	Future vision educational society	Bhiwani, Jind, Kaithal, Panchkula	Construction, IT-ITeS, Logistics, Plumbing, Power, Capital goods
14.	Guidance point education society	Ambala, Karnal, Kurukshetra, Mewat, Palwal	Logistics, Media and Entertainment, Power, Healthcare
15.	Genuine Promoters	Gurugram	Agriculture, IT-ITeS, Media and Entertainment
16.	GS Techno Innovation Pvt. Ltd.	Faridabad	Electronic and hardware
17.	Ganga Sagar Homes Pvt. Ltd.	Jhajjar	Beauty and wellness, Life science
18.	Gayatri Group of Education	Jhajjar, Palwal	Persons with disability
19.	Gramin Kaushal	Rohtak	Retail
20.	ICA EDU skills Pvt. Ltd.	Ambala, Karnal, Kurukshetra, Panchkula, Yamunanagar	Automotive, Construction, IT-ITeS, Retail, Tourism & Hospitality, Healthcare, Apparel, Logistics, Electronic and hardware, Telecom, Green Jobs
21.	Innovision Limited	Faridabad, Gurugram, Mahendragarh, Mewat, Rewari	Apparel, Logistics, Retail, Telecom, IT-ITeS
22.	Innovious Technologies Private Limited	Sirsa	Electronics and hardware, Leather
23.	Kaushal Shala Foundation	Karnal	IT-ITeS
24.	Kgm Immigration and educational consultant's Pvt. Ltd.	Mewat	Logistics, Power
25.	Life foundation	Yamunanagar	Persons with disability
26.	Lala Kundan Lal Memorial Society	Faridabad, Fatehabad, Gurugram, Sonapat	Logistics, Media and entertainment, Retail, Capital goods, Power
27.	Maruti Suzuki India Ltd.	Gurugram,	Automotive, Fitter, Capital goods
28.	Maa Saraswati Educational Trust	Panchkula	Apparel, Beauty and wellness, IT-ITeS Management
29.	National association for the blind employment and training	Gurugram,	Persons with disability
30.	Nav Jyoti Global Solutions Pvt. Ltd.	Gurugram,	Persons with disability
31.	National paramedical sciences society	Kurukshetra	Apparel, IT-ITeS, Retail
32.	Orion Edutech private limited	Bhiwani, Jhajjar, Panipat, Rohtak, Sirsa	Apparel, Beauty and wellness, Construction, Electronic and hardware, Telecom, Retail, Automotive, Tourism & hospitality, Healthcare
33.	Om Vijay Charitable Trust	Hisar, Jind	Apparel, Electronic and hardware, IT-ITeS, Media and entertainment
34.	Om Sai educational trust	Panchkula	Persons with disability

35.	PM skill center	Panipat	Apparel, Logistics
36.	Prerna Engineering Education Group	Sonipat	Persons with disability
37.	Rhombas Educational and Technical Society	Bhiwani, Hisar, Sirsa	Logistics, Electronic and hardware, Power, Beauty and wellness, Apparel, Power
38.	Rishan Infoskills Pvt. Ltd.	Charkhi Dadri, Palwal	Construction, IT-ITeS, Logistics
39.	Raj educational and technical society	Jind	Logistics, Power
40.	Rao Net Ram education society	Mahendragarh	Agriculture, Apparel, Electronics and hardware
41.	Rite computer education	Mewat	Gems and Jewellery
42.	Ram Gopal educational society	Rohtak	Logistics, Power
43.	Shiv education society	Ambala, Karnal	Electronic and hardware, Logistics, Media and entertainment, Power
44.	Skills and you consultants private limited	Ambala, Panipat, Yamunanagar	Retail
45.	Stellar edge solutions Pvt. Ltd.	Ambala, Jind	Beauty and wellness, Apparel, IT-ITeS, Logistics
46.	Samaj Sewa Federation	Fatehabad	Media and entertainment, Power
47.	Satyam shivam build vision private limited	Bhiwani, Jind, Mahendragarh	Electronic and hardware, Media and entertainment, Persons with disability
48.	Soft dot technologies private limited	Faridabad,	Apparel, Logistics
49.	Shri Ram skills development Pvt. Ltd.	Bhiwani, Hisar, Jhajjar	Construction, Electronic and hardware, Healthcare, Apparel, Power
50.	Sant Mahavir Jain Trust	Jind	Apparel
51.	SBS skill training center	Panipat	Logistics, Power
52.	Shrimati Kamlesh Devi Educational society	Karnal	Healthcare, Telecom
53.	Sachdeva colleges Limited	Mewat	Logistics, Power
54.	The Unique Foundation	Gurugram	Aerospace and aviation
55.	The Bharat scouts and guides	Mewat	Automotive electrician, Domestic IT helpdesk attendant, Courier delivery executive
56.	The Gulab Fruit and vegetable Growers and Marketing cooperative societies Ltd.	Sonipat	Agriculture
57.	Valex Institute	Jind	Persons with disability
58.	VOC skills	Mahendragarh	Persons with disability
59.	Webtech universal learning Pvt. Ltd.	Bhiwani, Rewari	BFSI, Retail, Automotive

(Annexure 3)

Table-4 Placement Performance of Training Partners

Sr. no	Training partner	TC Name	Placement Performance	1 st Month Record closure for Validation	Training Centers Qualifying for Performance Based Target Reallocation
1.	Centum Work Skills India Limited	GHS InfoTech Private Limited-Ambala	84.0%	No	No
		ARP Institute-Hisar	74.2%	No	No
		CWSI PMKK- Kaithal	90.1%	No	Yes
		Shri Guru Brahmanand Trust and Bani-Kaithal	74.6%	Yes	No
		CWSI PMKK-Hisar	93.7%	No	Yes
		CWSI PMKK Jind	90.3%	Yes	Yes
		PMKK- Fatehabad	89.1%	Yes	Yes
		PMKK- Sirsa	0.0%	No	Yes
2	Aitmc ventures Pvt. Ltd	Aitmc Sisai Bolen-Hisar	87.8%	Yes	No
		Aitmc Goriwala-Sirsa	87%	Yes	No
		Aitmc Ramkumar-Sirsa	92.9%	Yes	No
		Aitmc Chautala-Sirsa	89.6%	Yes	Yes
		Aitmc Chautala 1- Sirsa	100%	Yes	No
		Aitmc –Hisar	88.7%	Yes	No
		Aitmc Chopta 1	84.1%	Yes	No
		Shivm Institute	97%	Yes	No
		Aitmc –Sardulgard	100%	Yes	No
		Aitmc Kanya Prathmic Pathshala	96.9%	Yes	No
		Aitmc Skill Development Institute	82.2%	Yes	Yes
3	Orion Edutech Private Limited	Orion Edutech-Bhiwani	32.7%	No	No
		Orion PMKK-Jhajjar	43.3%	No	No
		PMKK- Rohtak	59.9%	No	No
		Orion Edutech-Panipat	47.4%	No	No
		PMKK-Sonipat	39.9%	No	No
4	B.R.M. Education and Welfare Society	New Star Skill Development Centre-Fatehabad	71.8%	Yes	No
		B.R.M. Society-Mother Teresa Skill Development Institute-Fatehabad	83.0%	Yes	No
		B.R.M. Skill Development Institute-Siswal (Hisar)	90.0%	Yes	Yes
		B.R.M. Education and Welfare Society-Fatehabad	80.7%	Yes	No
		New Star Skill Development Institute- Fatehabad	91.5%	Yes	No
		B.R.M. Society-SND Skill Development Institute-Saniana (Fatehabad)	81.8%	Yes	Yes
		B.R.M. Skill Development Institute- Fatehabad	81.7%	Yes	Yes
		India Skill Development Institute-Fatehabad	71.6%	No	No
		Ganpati Skill Development Institute-Hisar	75.0%	No	No

		Quality Skill Development Institute-Hisar	79.0%	No	No
		Scottish Skill Development Institute-Hisar	89.7%	Yes	No
		Hisar Skill Development Institute	79.3%	Yes	Yes
		Takshila Kaushal Vikas Center-Fatehabad	84.7%	No	No
		Master Mind Skill Development Institute-Fatehabad	74.8%	Yes	No
		Daksh Skill Development Institute-Hisar	78.0%	No	No
		Takshila Kaushal Vikas Center-Fatehabad	72.9%	Yes	Yes
		Bala Ji Skill Development Institute-Fatehabad	84.0%	Yes	No
5	Advance Smart Skills Private Limited (Mahendragarh)	Bala Ji Computer and Job Training Center	75.6%	No	No
		Guro Dronacharya Skill Development Institute	65.6%	No	No
		BMD Training Center	79.0%	No	No
		Baba Rupadas Skill Center	76.7%	No	No
6	BDM Institute Skill Development (Bhiwani)	BDM Institute Skill Development	60.5%	No	No
		Happy Education Skill Development	100%	Yes	No
		BDM Institute Skill Development	100%	No	No
		Rajendera Skill Development	100%	No	No
		Baba Phool Nath Skiksha Samiti	100%	Yes	No
		Baba Phool Nath Skill Development	97.7%	Yes	No
7	Brilliant Education Society	Brilliant Education Society-Yamunanagar	40.6%	No	No
8	C.R. Dadhich Memorial Society	Aadarsh Skill Education Institute-Sirsa	69.5%	No	No
		Oxford Skill Development Institutions-Fatehabad	97.6%	Yes	No
		Panchal Skill Training Center-Faridabad	0.0%	No	No
		Gurukul Computer Academy-Bhiwani	81.0%	No	No
		Srishtri Kaushal Vikas Training Center-Faridabad	89.6%	Yes	No
		Siwatch Skill Training Center-Hisar	35.9%	No	No
		Satyam Skill Center-Fatehabad	73.1%	Yes	No
		Domestic Carrier Campus-Kaithal	82.1%	Yes	No
		Komal Skill Training Center-Fatehabad	88.1%	Yes	No
		Ujjawal Group of Education Institute	74.0%	Yes	No

		Dadhich Skill Center	89.7%	Yes	No
9	Directorate of Indian Army Veterans	ASTC-Ambala Cantt	0.0%	No	No
		ASTC-Chandimandir	0.0%	No	No
10	DP Education Society (Faridabad)	LSDC	71.7%	No	No
		Laxmi Skill Development Centre	86.4%	No	No
		DP Education Skill Center	86.3%	No	No

Sources: <http://pmkvyofficial.org/Target-allocation.aspx>

(Annexure 4)

Table-5 Categories of Target Re-allocation

Training partner	Training center	Categories					
		A	B	C	D	E	F
Centum Work Skills India Limited	GHS InfoTech Private Limited-Ambala					✓	
	ARP Institute-Hisar					✓	
	CWSI PMKK- Kaithal						✓
	Shri Guru Brahmanand Trust and Bani-Kaithal					✓	
	CWSI PMKK-Hisar						✓
	CWSI PMKK Jind						✓
	PMKK- Fatehabad						✓
	PMKK- Sirsa						✓
Aitmc Ventures Pvt. Ltd.	Aitmc Sisai Bolan-Hisar	✓					
	Aitmc Goriwala-Sirsa	✓					
	Aitmc Ramkumar-Sirsa	✓					
	Aitmc Chautala-Sirsa	✓					
	Aitmc Chautala 1-Sirsa	✓					
	Aitmc –Hisar	✓					
	Aitmc Chopta 1	✓					
	Shivm Institute	✓					
	Aitmc –Sardulgard	✓					
	Aitmc Kanya Prathmic Pathshala	✓					
	Aitmc Skill Development Institute	✓					
Orion Edutech Private Limited	Orion Edutech-Bhiwani						✓
	Orion PMKK-Jhajjar						✓
	PMKK- Rohtak						✓
	Orion Edutech-Panipat						✓
	PMKK-Sonipat						✓
B.R.M. Education and Welfare Society	New Star Skill Development Centre-Fatehabad	✓					
	B.R.M. Society-Mother Teresa Skill Development Institute-Fatehabad					✓	
	B.R.M. Skill Development Institute-Siswal (Hisar)	✓					
	B.R.M. Education and Welfare Society-Fatehabad					✓	
	New Star Skill Development Institute- Fatehabad					✓	
	B.R.M. Society-SND Skill	✓					

	Development Institute- Saniana (Fatehabad)						
	B.R.M. Skill Development Institute- Fatehabad	✓					
	India Skill Development Institute-Fatehabad		✓				
	Ganpati Skill Development Institute-Hisar		✓				
	Quality Skill Development Institute-Hisar		✓				
	Scottish Skill Development Institute-Hisar		✓				
	Hisar Skill Development Institute	✓					
	Takshila Kaushal Vikas Center-Fatehabad		✓				
	Master Mind Skill Development Institute-Fatehabad					✓	
	Daksh Skill Development Institute-Hisar		✓				
	Takshila Kaushal Vikas Center-Fatehabad	✓					
	Bala Ji Skill Development Institute-Fatehabad		✓				
Advance Smart Skills Private Limited (Mahendragarh)	Bala Ji Computer and Job Training Center				✓		
	Guro Dronacharya Skill Development Institute					✓	
	BMD Training Center				✓		
	Baba Rupadas Skill Center				✓		
BDM Institute Skill Development (Bhiwani)	BDM Institute Skill Development					✓	
	Happy Education Skill Development				✓		
	BDM Institute Skill Development		✓				
	Rajendera Skill Development		✓				
	Baba Phool Nath Skiksha Samiti		✓				
	Baba Phool Nath Skill Development		✓				
Brilliant Education Society	Brilliant Education Society - Yamunanagar					✓	
C.R. Dadhich Memorial Society	Aadarsh Skill Education Institute-Sirsa					✓	
	Oxford Skill Development Institutions-Fatehabad					✓	
	Panchal Skill Training Center-Faridabad					✓	
	Gurukul Computer Academy-Bhiwani					✓	
	Srishtri Kaushal Vikas Training Center-Faridabad		✓				
	Siwatch Skill Training Center-Hisar					✓	
	Satyam Skill Center- Fatehabad					✓	

	Domestic Carrier Campus-Kaithal					<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
	Komal Skill Trainng Center-Fatehabad					<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
	Ujjawal Group of Education Institute					<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
	Dadhich Skill Center					<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Directorate of Indian Army Veterans	ASTC, Ambala Cantt					<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
	ASTC, Chandimandir					<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
DP Education Society	LSDC		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>				
	Laxmi Skill Development Centre		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>				
	DP Education Skill Center		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>				